

CO₂-LASER-ASSISTED PRODUCTION OF HYBRID FIBER-REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

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1 Abstract

To fully exploit the potential of fiber-reinforced thermoplastic composites (FRTC) and to achieve a broad industrial application, automated manufacturing systems are crucial. Furthermore investigations at Fraunhofer IPT have proven that the use of laser system technology in processing FRTC enables to achieve high throughput, quality, flexibility, reproducibility and out-of-autoclave processing simultaneously. Currently more than 90% of the fiber-reinforced plastics (FRP) in Europe are glass fiber-reinforced [1]. Due to these facts the next logical step to maximize the potential of laser-assisted processing is its extension towards glass fiber-reinforced thermoplastics (GFRTC) as well as hybrid composites, meaning the combined processing of glass and carbon fiber-reinforced with non-reinforced thermoplastics.

2 Introduction

Thermosetting FRPs still dominate the market due to their processability with traditional methods, e.g. manual lamination and autoclaving, at ambient temperatures. Pipes, antenna masts and tanks made of carbon or glass fiber-reinforced thermosets are nowadays produced using filament winding. In this process, one or several carbon or glass yarns, so called rovings, are impregnated (e.g. pulled through a resin bath) and wound layer by layer and under a defined yarn tension around a rotating core. Nowadays 80% - 90% of all advanced aircraft structures made of carbon fiber-reinforced plastics are based on prepreg (pre-impregnated fiber) materials and are consolidated using autoclaves [2]. Industrial state of the art is the automated processing of unidirectional fiber-reinforced prepregs via tape laying of single broad tapes (e.g. prepreg width of

300 mm) for the manufacture of 2D or contoured structures, like wings and vertical and horizontal tail planes. The use of thermosetting FRPs leads, however, to high energy costs due to the energy-consuming cold storage when using thermosetting prepregs (preimpregnated fibres) and to necessary energy- and time-consuming (several hours) curing process steps in special ovens.

3 State of the art

The major advantage of laser-assisted tape placement is that with high precision, quality and speed composite tapes can be placed and fused in any position with every fiber-orientation. By this method tailored fully consolidated components and tailored blanks can be produced directly. However for mass application purposes it is beneficial to mainly local reinforce fabric-reinforced blanks as well as components using tape with unidirectional fiber reinforcement according to the load case. The combination of mass blank production, thermoforming and local reinforcement (either part or blank) results in high productivity and an excellent price to performance ratio of the components. In addition it enables an enormous technical and economic freedom of design. The costly carbon fibers are applied only there where they achieve the highest benefit and take the major loads, whereas the base panels achieve the economical (plastic base blank or tube, GFRP base blank or tube) boundary conditions.

During tape placement the prepregs are unreel from a tape spool and fed by a feed unit into the nip point, see Fig. 1. The surface of the fed tape as well as the one of the already laid down material get heated up over melting temperature using laser radiation shortly before contact with each other. Applying a compaction force using an optionally

heated or cooled consolidation roller the melt up tape gets completely consolidated in situ with the part to be produced without the need for subsequent curing steps. The main difference between laser-assisted tape placement and winding is the use of a rotating mandrel in the case of tape winding, see Fig. 1 and Fig. 2. Over the last decade laser systems have been proven to be the most energy-efficient, precise and cost-effective method for tape placement in a lot of benchmarks [3][4]. For years Fraunhofer IPT has developed the diode laser-assisted tape placement and winding to process carbon fiber-reinforced thermoplastic composites (CFRTC). Unfortunately this technology cannot be transferred one to one to process milky transparent GFRTC preregs. Also the reinforcement of pure non-colored thermoplastic components or the use of non-colored thermoplastics as first layer or liner for winding processes is limited.

Fig. 1. Principle of laser-assisted tape placement

Fig. 2. Principle of laser-assisted tape winding

4 Approaches

Due to the short wavelength (approx. 980 nm) and therefore high transmission less than 20% of the diode laser energy is induced as heat into non-colored GFRTC or pure thermoplastics unlike using a CO₂-laser (10,6 μm) with more than 90% laser absorption. Also the absorption of CO₂-laser radiation at the surface compared to volume absorption of diode laser radiation is beneficial for the interlaminar joining of GFRTC. Fraunhofer IPT is currently developing and investigating the CO₂-laser-assisted tape placement and winding including new system, beam guiding, process and temperature measuring technology to enable a resource and energy efficient mass production of hybrid composites. To cover a broad scope of possible applications for CO₂-laser-assisted processing of glass fiber-reinforced preregs two different thermoplastic matrix materials are investigated. Polypropylen (PP) is one of the most common standard thermoplastic materials. PP is furthermore available at low cost. Polyphenylene Sulfid (PPS) is a widely used high performance engineering plastic with good chemical and heat resistance.

5 Thermo-optical properties of GFRTC preregs

When processing and combining FRTCs reinforced with different fibers using laser-assisted tape placement the thermo-optical properties of the used preregs as well as the base materials is of the essence. In particular the different properties of non-colored preregs as well as liners and other non-reinforced base materials compared to completely black carbon fiber-reinforced preregs is striking. Although the black color of CFRTC tapes is mainly based on the black carbon fibers the color and therefore the absorption properties of glass fiber-reinforced tapes is based on a mixture of the colors of the matrix material, the fibers, the added particles as well as effects due to optical refraction at the boundary layers between the different materials. The optical properties of the processed tapes have a major influence not only on the energy input during laser irradiation but also on the accuracy of non-contact temperature measurement. Especially the combined processing of these materials with completely different thermo-optical properties using laser-assisted tape placement or winding has to be investigated. Due to these reasons a sufficient and

efficient laser energy input during tape placement and winding of non-colored glass fiber-reinforced or non-reinforced thermoplastics comes with some major challenges which are being dealt with and investigated at Fraunhofer IPT using CO₂-lasers as an alternative laser source. Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 show the results of the optical analysis of PP and PPS based glass fiber-reinforced prepregs using FTIR and UV-Vis spectroscopy. As shown the absorption of both materials is very low at the wave length range of diode laser radiation. In contrast CO₂-laser radiation is absorbed by more than 95 %.

Fig. 3. Optical analysis of non-colored PP-GF tape

Fig. 4. Optical analysis of non-colored PPS-GF tape

Further investigations, an extended literature research as well as theoretical considerations have led to the conclusion that the CO₂-laser radiation is not completely absorbed by the thermoplastic material but also partly by the glass fibers when processing GFRTC tapes, see Fig. 5. In the literature there are different approaches to describe the effects of absorption of laser radiation of plastic materials. Commonly the absorption of solids is divided into two definitions [5]. In case of surface absorption the penetration depth is significantly smaller than the material thickness of the processed tapes of 0.25 mm. In the case of volume absorption the material gets penetrated almost along its entire thickness. At the other hand a typical penetration depth for CO₂-laser radiation in polymers is specified with 100 μm [6][7] (ca. half of the tape thickness). However, the research in the field of laser-assisted processing of thermoplastics was so far mainly focused on laser welding of homogenous non-reinforced polymers. Due to this not all the findings can be used directly to explain the thermo-optical effects during laser-assisted tape placement and winding which means interlaminar welding of fiber-reinforced prepregs with a thickness of only 0.15 to 0.25 mm and a polymer boundary layer, if existent, with a thickness of only a few microns. Based on a comparison of the process behavior of the non-colored GFRTC prepregs with the one of CFRTC or colored GFRTC as well as the needed laser power for processing the tapes the laser absorption mechanisms for the special case CO₂-laser-assisted tape placement of thin fiber-reinforced tapes could be derived, see Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Laser absorption mechanisms depending on the material and the used laser source

Due to these results it is to assume that when processing very thin glass fiber-reinforced thermoplastic prepregs the CO₂-laser radiation gets mainly absorbed by the first fiber layers and only partly by the pure thermoplastic layer at the surface. The penetration depth of CO₂-laser radiation of only ca. 100 μm in solid polymers however allows the use of non-colored and non-reinforced layers or liners as first layer which opens completely new fields of application for tape placement for example in regard to local reinforcement, the first layer fixation problem and the use of foils as functionalized surfaces.

6 CO₂-laser-assisted tape placement and winding

6.1 Test setup

For first process parameter investigations and to prove the feasibility of CO₂-laser-assisted tape placement and winding of a combination of non-colored glass and carbon fiber-reinforced thermoplastic prepregs with non-reinforced base materials a test bench was developed and assembled, see Fig. 6. This test bench consists of a tape laying unit, a mirror based laser beam guidance, a laboratory scale CO₂-laser shaping and homogenizing optics, a non-contact temperature measuring system as well as a rudimentary closed-loop laser power control. As basis for the test bench an existing diode laser-assisted tape placement unit was used without the diode laser optics. This allows a direct comparison of the process results with the findings regarding diode laser-assisted tape placement and winding since all the mechanical components and the geometrical relations are the same. To adapt the orientation of the fibers within the produced parts the tapes can be laid down in different directions. To do so the tape laying unit of the test bench including the laser optics can be rotated around the optical axis of the incoming vertical raw CO₂-laser beam within certain limitations without influencing the laser spot in the working plane. The shown test setup is mounted to a gantry unit with integrated CO₂-laser source as well as a beam guidance based on flying optics. A winding axis which is part of the gantry unit allows the investigation of tape winding.

Fig. 6. Test bench setup for CO₂-laser-assisted tape laying and winding

6.2 CO₂-laser beam shaping and homogenization

Due to the large wave length of the used CO₂-laser radiation the use of transparent optical components is limited. Due to the potential harmfulness of ZnSe optics in case of damage only reflective optics are used to guide, shape and homogenize the CO₂-laser raw beam. The intensity distribution of laser beams with Gaussian intensity distribution can basically be homogenized using two methods, Field-Mapping and Beam-Integration [8]. For the test bench setup Field-Mapping was realized using two aspherical reflectors, see Fig. 7. The raw laser beam is shaped by the aspheres into a rectangular spot as well as homogenized over its height and width. The polynomial equations for the aspherical surfaces of the reflectors were especially calculated using ZEMAX® in accordance to the measured beam profile of the raw CO₂-laser beam, the distances between the optical elements as well as the working plane and the required laser spot size. By adjusting the distance between the two aspheres it is possible to adapt the height of the laser spot in the working plane. The dependency on the condition and the exact alignment of the raw beam is a major disadvantage of the Field-Mapping method. The main advantage of this method is the absence of interference phenomena when using coherent radiation.

Fig. 7. CO₂-laser beam shaping and homogenization using the Field Mapping method

In contrast misalignments have only minor effects on the shaped beam when using the Beam Integration method, see Fig. 8. Beam Integration is based on the principle that the inbound distribution gets split into single distribution shares which are subsequently homogenized through superposition with integrator lenses. Micro lens arrays or faceted mirrors can be used for beam integration with the disadvantage of possible interferences when using coherent radiation [8][9].

Fig. 8. CO₂-laser beam shaping and homogenization using the Beam Integration method [9]

Fig. 9 shows the measured intensity profile of the profile of the shaped and homogenized laser spot in the working plane using the test bench setup with beam shaping according to the Field Mapping method. The intensity distribution of the shaped laser spot was measured in the style of acrylic mode burns. Only that in this case the burned-in laser beam profile was digitalized using a profilometer. It has to be considered that the beam guidance is not

completely free of misalignments and pollutions of the reflecting mirrors. Nevertheless a laser spot with a shape and homogenization level sufficient for first process trials could be realized. Yet the strong dependency of the output beam from the input conditions is obvious.

Fig. 9. Field Mapping method – acrylic burn digitalized using a profilometer

In Fig. 10 exemplary possible spot sizes using the CO₂-laser-homogenizer-optics with active zoom function newly developed by the Chair for Technology of Optical Systems of the RWTH Aachen are demonstrated using the red laser beam of a HeNe laser source. Compared to Fig. 9 edges of the spot are far sharper and the intensity distribution is far more homogenous.

Fig. 10. Beam Integration method – Laser spot visualized using a HeNe laser source [9]

7 Process investigations

The analysis of the thermo-optical properties of PP-GF and PPS-GF tapes showed that non-colored glass fiber-reinforced thermoplastic prepregs can be processed virtually in the same way than carbon fiber-reinforced thermoplastics when using CO₂-laser radiation. Also for example non-reinforced thermoplastic liners can be efficiently molten up at the surface. Since CFRTC can be processed with both diode and CO₂-lasers CO₂-laser-assisted tape placement can be used to produce hybrid components combining CFRTC, GFRTC and pure non-reinforced polymers. The key process parameters are the temperature, the compaction force, the ratio of the irradiation length on the tape and the already laid down material as well as the feed rate. To quantify the process results during tape placement and winding the interlaminar shear strength is measured using two wedge peel tests, see Fig. 11 and Fig. 12.

By comparing the reached wedge resistance of samples produced with different process parameters it is possible to conduct a process parameter investigation. Microscopies of cross sectional preparations are additionally used for a qualitative assessment of the quality of the produced samples. Together with experimental design and methodology the main process influences as well as their interactions can be identified and an optimized process parameter set derived.

Fig. 11. Interlaminar shear strength test setup for tape placed samples

Fig. 12. Interlaminar shear strength test setup for tape wound samples

8 First project results

First process parameter investigations were conducted using the CO₂-laser test bench setup described above to produce first samples. By doing so an optimized process parameter set for CO₂-laser-assisted tape winding of glass fiber-reinforced PP and PPS prepregs in combination with PP liners and carbon fiber-reinforced PPS prepregs could be found and first demonstration parts produced. Fig. 13 shows a first wound hybrid pipe consisting of inner layers made of non-colored PPS-GF tapes reinforced with PPS-CF tapes using CO₂-laser-assisted tape winding.

Fig. 13. Tape wound and placed hybrid samples using CO₂-laser radiation

Fig. 14 shows a corresponding cross sectional preparation where a good consolidation between the glass and carbon fiber-reinforced thermoplastic matrix material can be observed. The quality of the interlaminar joint can be observed in Fig. 13. On the left side of the picture a diffusion of a few carbon fibers into the glass fiber-reinforced area can be seen. This is good evidence for extended diffusion effects beyond the boundary layers of the GFRTC and CFRTC prepregs. The dark areas within the

PPS-CF (upper tape) are mainly the result of the cross sectional preparation. For cross sectional preparations of glass fiber-reinforced thermoplastics normally other methods and impregnation resins are used than for carbon fiber-reinforced thermoplastics. Due to this the cross sectional preparation of hybrid parts is based on a compromise which can lead to defects in one or both materials.

Fig. 14. Microscopy of cross sectional preparations of tape wound hybrid PPS-CF/ PPS-GF samples

Fig. 15. Microscopy of cross sectional preparations of tape placed hybrid PPS-CF/ PPS-GF samples

Fig. 16 shows the fully consolidated defect free interlaminar bonding of glass fiber-reinforced tapes onto a liner made of non-reinforced PP. At the one hand the used CO₂-laser radiation gets fully absorbed not only at the surface of the PP-GF tape but also at the non-colored surface of the PP pipe which leads to an energy efficient process. The fact that the CO₂-laser irradiation has a penetration depth of up to 100 µm within non-reinforced non-colored thermoplastic materials ensures at the other hand a melt volume high enough for optimal interlaminar bonding.

Fig. 16. Microscopy of cross sectional preparations of tape wound hybrid PP-GF/ PP-Liner samples

9 Development of a new CO₂-laser tape placement and winding system

The theoretical and preliminary experimental research work using a CO₂-laser test bench lead to first results and a solid knowledge base. Based on this and the gained experience the requirements for the development of completely new tape placement system for CO₂-laser-assited tape winding of glass fiber-reinforced thermoplastics in combination with CFRTC and non-reinforced plastics were derived, see Fig. 17.

Fig. 17. System design for CO₂-laser-assisted tape placement and winding

The newly developed, designed and build up CO₂-laser tape placement and winding system is shown in Fig. 18. A HeNe laser source was used to visualize the shaped and homogenized laser spot in the working area. At present the new system is getting put into operation and will be used for additional process development and optimizations.

Fig. 18. Build up system for CO₂-laser-assisted tape placement and winding

10 Conclusion and outlook

An optimized process parameter set for CO₂-laser-assisted tape winding of glass fiber-reinforced PP and PPS prepregs together with CFRTC and a thermoplastic liner as winding core could be found and first demonstration parts produced using the preliminary test bench for CO₂-laser tape placement and winding.

The newly developed tape winding system consists of a new flexible CO₂-laser beam guiding to allow the use of all 5 axes of an existing gantry unit at Fraunhofer IPT. Furthermore an active CO₂-laser optics developed by the Chair for Technology of Optical Systems of the RWTH Aachen has been integrated. This optics will allow the active adaption of the width, height and angle of the homogenized laser spot. The use of CO₂-laser radiation in combination with spot dimensions adaptable in a wide range will widen the scope of research and allow completely new process investigations on the influence of these factors on the interlaminar weld quality. Furthermore special real time and highly accurate pyrometers specially adapted for CO₂-laser-assisted tape placement will be used for in process

closed-loop control of the laser power as well as the irradiation angle. An overall industry ready control architecture and closed-loop control system will be developed and interconnected with all subsystems, e.g. laser source, gantry unit etc. The aim is to implement a turnkey CO₂-laser-assisted tape winding system for the efficient and economic production of hybrid that means glass and carbon fiber-reinforced thermoplastic components.

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